

CATALYTIC TAR REFORMING WITH SEWAGE SLUDGE CHAR OF A PRODUCER GAS FROM FLUIDIZED BED CO-GASIFICATION OF SEWAGE SLUDGE AND WOOD

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ABSTRACT: Fluidized bed gasification of sewage sludge is a promising method for its valorisation due to the fuel flexibility of the process. The main drawbacks are the impurities present in the producer gas, with a high tar content, and its low calorific value. In this study, sewage sludge and wood mixtures are gasified in a fluidized bed. A tar cracking reactor is used to reduce the amount of tars and to increase the calorific value of the producer gas. Sewage sludge char is employed for tar cracking with a real producer gas, showing the feasibility of the process with a tar conversion of about 80% at the beginning. The test was conducted for several hours and tar deactivation was observed, which lead to a decrease of tar conversion to about 35% after 5 hours. Reactivating the char with steam increases again the tar conversion up to 84%, however, the subsequent deactivation was found to be faster compared to the one for fresh char. First tests using char from the gasification process in the tar cracking unit also show promising results.

Keywords: sewage sludge, tar removal, char, gas cleaning, fluidized bed, gasification

1 INTRODUCTION

Gasification is a very flexible alternative for biomass conversion, including also sewage sludge valorization, because of the many uses of the producer gas. Possible applications include gas engines or fuel cells to produce electricity, methanation or Fischer-Tropsch for biofuel production. Besides, the recovery of phosphorus from sewage sludge is an issue of increasing importance. An advantage of sewage sludge gasification is that recovery of the phosphorous from the residual char and ashes is easy compared to combustion because the phosphorous is in an acid soluble form [1]. Fluidized bed reactors are better suited for gasification of sewage sludge compared to fixed bed gasifiers since fuel handling is easier and this technology enables a better mixing of the feedstock with the gasification agent. Therefore, fluidized bed gasification of sewage sludge is the focus of this work.

Although there are many advantages of fluidized bed gasification, like a very homogeneous temperature distribution and a better upscaling, a big problem is the comparably high tar content in the producer gas. This high tar content can lead to blocking and fouling due to tar condensation at lower temperatures or catalyst deactivation. For most applications, the tar content of a producer gas obtained in a fluidized bed gasifier is too high for a direct usage [2] and needs to be lowered by either primary (treatment inside the gasifier) or secondary measures (hot or cold gas cleaning after the gasifier) [3]. Furthermore, the tars contain significant amounts of energy that can be transferred to the fuel gas as H₂, CO and CH₄, which will also increase the heating value of the gas [4]. In this work, tar cracking with a secondary tar cracking unit is investigated to check if the tar content can be reduced to facilitate the use of the gas for applications where low tar contents are required.

In literature, several studies of downstream tar cracking with char can be found. However, in most cases, only tar model compounds are used [5]. It is known that the tar conversion depends on the mixture of species in the gas stream and that tar conversion and deactivation behaviour in the range of 700–900 °C is improved by the presence of reforming agents like H₂O or CO₂. Therefore, experiments using a real producer gas are needed to get a

deeper understanding of the process. In the present study, a real producer gas obtained by fluidized bed gasification of a mixture of wood and sewage sludge as fuel was treated in a fixed bed tar cracking reactor. Sewage sludge pellets were used as the parent material of the employed char for tar cracking. Sewage sludge contains a comparably high amount of minor elements such as Alkali and Alkaline Earth Metals, Fe, Al, Si and P which can improve the catalytic properties of the char [5].

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

In the following section, the experimental setup, the used analytics as well as the experimental procedure are explained in more detail.

2.1 Experimental setup

Figure 1: Continuous fluidized bed gasifier (A), producer gas conditioning unit (B, not visible), tar sampling set-up (C) and flare (D) to burn the gas.

Figure 1 shows the set-up used to conduct the experiments and a detailed flow chart can be seen in Figure 2. The producer gas is obtained in an allothermal fluidized bed gasifier (A). As feedstock, a mixture of 75 % wood and 25 % sewage-sludge pellets is used. The fuel feeding rate can be adjusted via a screw and was set to 300 g/h. The fuel tank is rinsed with a nitrogen flow for inertisation and to prevent wet producer gas to enter the fuel tank, which would lead to swelling of pellets.

Figure 2: Flow chart of the experimental set-up

The bed is operated at a temperature of 750 °C, using olivine as bed material. The gasification temperature is regulated so that the mean value of three thermocouples, whereof two are located in the bed and one is located just above the bed, equals the target temperature of 750 °C. The fluidized bed reactor is made of stainless steel and has a diameter of 80 mm in the bottom section where the bed is located and a freeboard region with a diameter of 250 mm. The whole system is pressurized to 2 bar absolute pressure and steam is used as fluidizing agent. The steam feeding rate is regulated via a needle valve and a measurement orifice and is set to a constant rate of 280 g/h. Particulate matter is removed with a heated sinter metal filter before the gas enters the tar cracking reactor via a pipe which is heated to 350 °C to avoid condensation of the tars. The tar cracking reactor consists of an electrically heated fixed bed reactor which is shown in Figure 3. The inner diameter of the reactor is 37.2 mm and the char can be filled up to a height of 600 mm. The temperature in the center of the reactor is measured at 16 different heights. The gas flow can be adjusted to go either through the gas conditioning unit (B, not visible in Figure 1) or directly to the flare (D) where it is burned. At the sample point right before the flare, a part of the gas is directed to the tar measurement set-up, where the tars are trapped in isopropanol and can afterwards be determined with a gravimetric method by evaporating the solvent. The exact procedure can be found in [6]. After the tar measurement, the gas components CO, CO₂, CH₄, O₂ and H₂ are measured with an ABB AO2020 gas analysis. The amount of N₂ is calculated by difference.

The sewage-sludge char used in the tar cracking reactor was obtained by performing pyrolysis of sewage sludge pellets in the same unit which is used for gas conditioning at a temperature of 800 °C with a constant N₂ flow of about 10 l/min.

2.2 Experimental procedure

The tar cracking reactor was filled with 360 g of sewage-sludge char and preheated to the operating temperature of 800 °C while being flushed with a small nitrogen flow to avoid combustion of the char. Afterwards, 0.81 Nm³/h producer gas were led through the char bed of 500 ml which results in a residence time in the bed of 0.56 s. The test was conducted for several hours and the tar content as well as the gas composition were measured at specific times. Each measurement period lasted for 40 minutes, during which the tar content and the gas composition are averaged.

Figure 3: Producer gas conditioning unit

Table I shows the fuel analysis of minor elements for sewage-sludge and the wood pellets. It can be seen that for sewage-sludge, all the minor elements are several orders of magnitude higher than for wood pellets. Also the ash content of sewage-sludge is about 100 times higher, which can lead to problems of ash sintering and formation of agglomerations in the fluidized bed [7].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The composition of the raw gas without going through the tar cracking unit was measured at the beginning and at the end of the measurement campaign. The measured values for the dry permanent gases as well as for the tars at the beginning (Raw gas I) and the end of the campaign (Raw gas II) are shown in Table 2. The gas composition is almost the same for the two measurements and therefore it can be assumed that the gas conditions were very stable during the measurement campaign. Besides, the measured compositions of permanent gases conducted during the tar sampling following the tar protocol were also very stable during each measurement period of 40 minutes and no short-term fluctuations were present.

The results for the gravimetric tar content are shown in Figure 4.a. The first bar shows the tar content of the raw gas of the fluidized bed gasifier without using the tar cracking reactor, which will be the reference value. A

value of 19.8 g/Nm³ was measured for the 25 % sewage sludge / 75 % wood feedstock mixture used in this study in the fluidized bed gasifier. This is almost twice the amount of tars obtained when using 100% wood pellets as feedstock while operating the gasifier at the same conditions. In the next bars, the mean values derived with the tar cracking unit after different cumulative measurement times are given. The stated time is the mean time of the measurement period. The first measurement with tar cracking, conducted after 20 minutes, shows a very high gravimetric tar conversion of about 80 %.

Table II: Dry gas composition and tar content of the raw producer gas without gas conditioning

		Raw gas I	Raw gas II
H₂	[vol.% dry]	31.1	30.2
N₂	[vol.% dry]	28.0	29.2
CO₂	[vol.% dry]	17.6	18.1
CO	[vol.% dry]	15.5	14.8
CH₄	[vol.% dry]	7.8	7.9
Tars	[g/Nm ³ dry]	19.8	19.8

Table I: Fuel properties (* dry basis)

Feedstock	Bulk-density	Fe*	Ca*	P*	Si*	Al*	S*	Mg*	Ash
[-]	[kg/m ³]	[mg/kg]	[m.%]						
Wood	655	43	788	55	199	36	67	133	0.37
Sewage-sludge	826	95200	35300	38600	25300	9920	10300	7450	40.4

Figure 4: Tar measurement results (a), H₂ content (b) and calorific value (c) for the raw gas during deactivation of fresh char and for steam-reactivated char.

However, deactivation took place later on and, after the experiment was running for about 320 minutes, the amount of conversion seemed to reach a constant value of around 35 %. After about 7 hours of use, the char was reactivated with a steam flow of 0.28 kg/h for 1 hour at a reactor temperature of 800 °C. The results after this reactivation showed also a very high tar conversion at the beginning, of 84 %. However, it dropped to a value of 51 % after only 100 minutes and it could be observed that deactivation of the reactivated char was faster. At the end of the measurement campaign, another reference measurement without the tar cracking reactor was conducted and it shows good reproducibility of the measuring methods and the stability in the raw producer gas composition.

In Figure 4.b and 4.c, the H₂ content and the calorific value of the wet gas are shown. For the measurements at 20, 100 and 220 minutes, it can clearly be seen that the H₂ yield and the calorific value are increased significantly when using the tar cracking reactor compared to the reference values of the raw gas. The increase in calorific value of the producer gas would facilitate its energetic valorisation. The increase of the H₂ content can be explained by the fact that H₂ (besides coke, CO and CO₂) is one of the major products of tar cracking [5]. The negative influence of char deactivation leads to a decrease of both values during the first deactivation period. After reactivating the char, again a higher H₂ yield and LHV are as well obtained due to the higher tar conversion.

Finally, also first tests were conducted using residual char from the gasification process (obtained using a mixture of sewage sludge and wood as fuel) as a catalyst, showing very promising results with conversion rates up to 93 %. The high potential of the application of gasification residuals like char for tar reforming was also recently highlighted by Buentello-Montoya et al. [8]. This is a very interesting alternative to expensive catalysts as the char is a by-product of every gasification plant and is sometimes considered a waste [5].

4 CONCLUSIONS

The present work is focused on producer gas treatment with sewage sludge char using a real producer gas obtained by gasification of a mixture of wood and sewage sludge pellets in a fluidized bed. It is experimentally shown that the use of a fixed bed tar cracking reactor can lead to high tar conversions of up to 80 %. The heating value of the producer gas is as well increased. The used sewage sludge char shows an increasing degradation over time, until a constant tar conversion of around 35 % is observed after several hours. Reactivating the char with steam led to an even better tar conversion of around 84 %. However, deactivation of the reactivated char took place faster than for the fresh char. Sewage sludge char, a by-product of gasification, is therefore a suitable tar cracking catalyst in this process if char reactivation is considered.

Future research should focus on optimizing the operation conditions in the tar cracking unit to avoid or minimize char deactivation. Experiments by Fuentes-Cano et al. [9] investigating catalytic decomposition of two model tars (toluene and naphthalene) showed that operating parameters like a higher temperature in the tar cracking unit and a high water content in the gas reduce

char deactivation. More experiments using a real producer gas should be conducted to further investigate whether conditions with e.g. higher temperatures or higher steam concentration in the producer gas can minimize char deactivation.

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7 LOGO SPACE

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